

The Effect of Using an Educational Program in the Development of Computer Skills among Mentally Disabled Students

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: July 04, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: August 05, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Educational Program, Computer Skills, Children with Disabilities</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6573991</p>	<p><i>The present study aimed at investigating the effect of using an educational program in the development of computer skills in children with mental disabilities, and the study sample consisted of (20) students, enrolled at the Arab Center for Special Education in Amman in the second semester of the academic year 2015/2016 aged around (13 years), they were selected purposefully by the researcher, and were assigned randomly to experimental and control groups, the experimental group consisting of two sections (one for males and one for females) studied using the educational program for the development of computer skills, and the control group consisting of two sections (one for males and one for females) studied using the Normal way. To achieve the objectives of the study, the researcher built an educational program for the development of computer skills and a school observation checklist. The results showed that there are no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) on the school observation checklist for the experimental group, and the results showed no statistically significant fundamental differences at the level ($\alpha = 0.05$) attributed to the variables of the study: (gender, interactive variable) The study recommends further studies and targeting other variables other than those contained in the study.</i></p>

Introduction

The usage of modern technologies was based in the use of technology in education and employment to make them an essential part of education, and not just an addition, and students with special needs part of this target harnessing educational technology in their education system, and this is what is approved by the recommendations of Arab Special Education Conference "Reality and Hope" (2005) (the need to adapt the modern technology in the service and the education of those with special needs, and the use of technology in achieving many of the goals of special education as a process of merging and the application of individual educational plan IEP dealing with the student individually based on the abilities and capacities, and all these goals will not be achieved without the availability of important elements such as efficient teacher and providing technical aimed means, material and technical support, and the removal of all obstacles to the use of technology in teaching these children.

In this regard, children with special needs Association CEC (2000) argues that teachers of special education must have a skill available in the use of educational technologies, and ability to provide an Educational environment purposeful contribute to building positive attitudes towards the use of tools and techniques for individuals with learning disabilities, the association also emphasizes that teachers help the students to use various means of communication that contribute to the integration of that category outside the community.

Teaching the mental disabled different skills that will help them to interact positively with the natural and social environments is considered a difficult task and due to the inability to use the most appropriate strategies based on learned principles of learning theories, and based on a sound understanding of the characteristics of these educators. (Saleh, 2007)

Children with mental disabilities Suffer from various linguistic difficulties, the most important is the slow language development, delayed speech, delayed language acquisition rules, poor vocabulary, and the simplicity of the linguistic structures, including not commensurate with the time of age, and so the level of their linguistic performance is much less than the normal peers of the same age (Quraiti, 2005)

And this is due to that children with mental disabilities suffer from an impaired ability to pay attention to high dispersion and reactivity, and this explains the lack of perseverance and they continue to position education as it took a while medium or suitable for ordinary period of time, poor attention and poor memory are two of the main reasons to poor apparent learning, and the degree of attention deficit

Directly proportional to the severity of the disability, the more severe the disability was increased shortage or poor concentration. (Al Sayed, A. & Bader, F. 2005)

Study Problem and its Significance

The special education consider students with special needs as an individual is characterized of needs and the characteristics and capabilities different from his peers from ordinary students, and stresses the importance of taking into account individual differences according to the student's needs and abilities and has his own requirements.

The use of computer is of a great importance in basic cognitive skills for mentally disabled if they have received good training, and if the coach teacher found a good training on computer as modern technique of learning techniques, it would lead to a reduction of the effort by him to repeat the information to the student and allow him to many of the multiple teaching methods that can diversify their teacher and take advantage of them. Because planning and education using computers is especially effective tool with students with mental disabilities (who are able to learn), plus it can be individualized and the frequency and organization of education by using the computer by offering the educational material. Therefore, the researcher is seeking in the current study to answer the following study main question: What is the effect of using an educational program in the development of computer skills in children with mental disabilities?

Questions of the Study

The researcher tried to answer the following questions:

1. Is there a fundamental difference between the performance of the experimental and control groups in computer skills, as measured by the study tools for children with mental disabilities?
2. Is there an interaction between gender and training program in the performance of children with mental disabilities in computer skills?

Operational definitions for the study terms

The researcher reviews the operational definitions of the terms of the study as follows:

Program: is an educational program based on the basic computer skills for the use of computer skill development in children with mental disabilities who are able to learn and that the researcher prepared

Mental Retardation: They are children who deviate from the functional level of mental performance as represented by the well-known IQ tests and which is below average performance, coupled with the inability to respond to the requirements of everyday social life (adaptive behavior), and shows through the stages of a child from birth to growth until the age of eighteen, as is evident from the observation records of mental disability center under study.

Computer Skills: is a collection of experiences, activities, and tasks process contained in the program prepared by the researcher in teaching computer skills for mentally disabled who are able to learn, which was adopted in the teaching of the experimental group

The limits of the study and its determinants

The results can be generalized in the light of the following limits:

Human limits: This study was limited to a sample of children with mental disabilities who are able to learn in Jordan, which has been selected deliberate way, and this limits the dissemination of the results of the study to other groups of children.

Time limits: The study was conducted during the second semester of the academic year 2015/2016

Spatial limits: This study was limited to children

Literature Review

Many researchers throughout the world conducted studies on using computer and technology in teaching in general and with students with disabilities in particular. The researcher reviewed some of these studies as follows:

The study of Ahmed Hussein (2009) aimed to identify the effectiveness of a proposed program of the Games of recreational self-concept of the development of the mentally disabled, the study sample consisted of 28 children of mentally disabled who are able to learn the proportion ratio of their intelligence ranged between (50-70) degree and between chronological age (15-18 years) they were divided into (8) Children of the pilot study, (20) children for the fundamental study and (10) children in each group experimental and control groups, the study

used self-concept scale for Tensi, the study found that recreational games have a positive effect on the self-concept development through the statistically significant differences between the two measurements pre and posttest, as well as through the differences in the post test for the experimental group.

Bin Taleb (2003) national study investigated the availability of educational technologies, and use, and to identify the obstacles that limit the use of those techniques in the teaching of art education at institutes of intellectual Education in the Kingdom.

Mousa (2002) conducted a study which was on the level of the Arab Gulf states aimed to identify the extent of the use of information and computer technology in basic education "primary stage" as well as to identify the difficulties that stand in the way of the application of this technology in education. The most important results of the study came in: the computer's ability to raise and improve the academic achievement level, and education using computer is still moving slowly in spite of its importance, and there is as yet no special computerized in primary material in spite of its importance in primary education in all study countries, and also the study concluded to that of the most important and the biggest obstacles is the lack of teacher training in the use of computers and employing it in the educational process, and there is also another important factor is the material cost prohibitive to provide devices.

Yusuf (2001) conducted a study aims to identify the training needs on computer software on a sample of intellectual education parameters and motor disabilities and dual disabilities "mental and motor" in the city of Riyadh. The findings have resulted in of the study for the limited number of computers in people with educational needs centers, and Microsoft Word program, and the power Point have got the highest degree of approval and use by teachers, but all the difficulties and obstacles that prevent the use of computer software in the view of the parameters were: lack of training, lack of computers in the classroom, as there is no encouragement from the employer, not the competent presence in the computer field, and the lack of educational software, and the lack of sufficient time to use the computer.

Ottolino (2000) also conducted a study on the "availability and use of technology by training teachers and teachers of early professions and hard of hearing," designed to detect the availability and use of technologies in teachers and teachers of early professions for the Deaf preparation programs and recipes hearing in Illinois, USA, and the obstacles that prevent the use of these techniques, and the results yielded that there is commonly high usage for printers, computers and CDs by the target group to complete the work on the study and to prepare lessons for learners, the study found that the obstacles to the use of techniques lies in the difficulty in obtaining them, as the vast majority of respondents indicated that they found (20) adequacy of skills important to teach, but these skills not taught in school programs also are not provided in the workshops, and that many of them have learned these skills autonomously.

Design and Methodology

Population of the study and its sample:

They are all children with mental disabilities who are able to learn at the Arab Center for the Disabled under the Ministry of Social Development in Amman enrolled in second semester 2015/2016 by diagnosis of (diagnosed early Disabilities Center in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan for mental disability) and their number is (40) students, aged about 13 years, divided into four sections , two sections were chosen as experimental group, and two sections as control the number of students in each group totaled 20 students, accordingly, the study sample consisted of 40 children with mental disabilities who are able to learn enrolled at the center. Members of the experimental group have undergone educational program for the development of computer skills and control group undergone the Normal program in the second semester of the year 2015/2016. Table (1) shows the distribution of members of the study.

Table (1): Distribution of members of the study on the experimental and control group

Group	Study members		Total
	Male	Female	
Experimental	4	6	10
Control	5	5	10

Total	9	11	20
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Study tools

Two tools were designed in the current study, and these tools are: educational program, and an observation checklist for Computer skills, the following is a detailed view of what has been conducted to design the study tools.

First: Educational Program

The program sessions based on theoretical frameworks that dealt with basic computer skills, principles and stages, as well as to take into account social, cognitive and motor and psychological characteristics of the mentally disabled, "who are able to learn."

The overall objective of the program: This program aims to recruit basic computer skills to the mentally disabled, "who are able to learn."

Program Requirements

- a. Teacher: active, prompt, and facilitator, and thinker, has good language, familiar with computer skills, and characteristics of the mentally disabled and the nature of their needs and well-informed.
- b. Educable learner.
- c. Learning environment: safe, natural, and supportive, and varied.
- d. The quality of learning: Various, and social, and fun, and collaborative.

The contents of the program:

The researcher build (7) educational activities for the development of basic computer skills and be implemented over fourteen sessions by two elite educational session for each activity and the design of each session determining the overall goal and its own objectives, as follows:

1. The mentally disabled child running computer.
2. The mentally disabled child can name computer parts (screen, mouse, and keyboard).
3. The mentally disabled child can run the word program
4. The mentally disabled child can run Word program to write (a letter, word, sentence, and paragraph).
5. The mentally disabled child knows the CD format.
6. The mentally disabled child refers to the disk driver "CD" place.
7. The mentally disabled child, run the CD garden figures to learn process of addition, subtraction "CD" alone.

The program validity:

The researcher introduced a program to ten educators at Jordanian universities of professors of special education, counseling and educational psychology, and specialists in the field of mental disability, special education, and computer and asked them to arbitration program in terms of: making sure the suitability of this program for a class that situation for them and the adequacy of the duration of the educational program, and the arbitrators agreed on the appropriateness of such a program for the category that it is put for.

Rating the program: the program effectiveness was evaluated by: School observation list for computer skills, a list of researchers' preparation.

Second: School observation checklist for computer skills:

to achieve the objectives of the study the checklist was prepared by researchers to measure the level of computer skills for children with mental disabilities who are able to learn by the teacher at the school, where the checklist of computer skills for children with mental disabilities in its final form consisted of (20) items describe the skill in terms of the degree of availability from the point of view of teachers in the school, and the number of alternatives for each skill added is four

in addition to the instructions and personal data page, and the teachers were asked to put the signal (x) in the appropriate box located in the answer sheet to the most appropriate response for each question.

Statistical treatments:

To answer the questions and hypotheses of the study, the statistical packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to calculate means, standard deviations, and test variability associated analysis (Ancova)

Results of the Study

This study aimed to investigate the effect of an educational program in the development of computer skills in children with mental disabilities, and to answer the first hypothesis, which states: "**There were no statistically**

significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the mean scores of mentally disabled children in the experimental and control groups in computer skills."

Means and standard deviations for improving computer skills in children with mental disabilities for pre/post responses were calculated, according to the variables of the study (teaching style and gender) and interactive variable between them (Teaching style x gender), so as in the table (2)

Table (2): Means and standard deviations for improving computer skills in children with mental disabilities for the pre/post responses, according to the variables of the study (teaching style and gender)

Teaching style	Gender	Computer skills (Educational Program)		Computer skills (The normal program)	
		Mean	Standard deviation	Mean	Standard deviation
Normal	Male	3.733	2.22	4.667	1.59
	female	5.067	1.22	5.667	1.63
	Total	4.400	1.89	5.167	1.66
Educational program	Male	3.133	2.17	8.533	1.36
	Female	4.267	1.28	8.733	1.28
	Total	3.700	1.84	8.633	1.30
Total	Male	3.433	2.18	6.600	2.44
	Female	4.667	1.30	7.200	2.12

Table (3): Amended arithmetic means and standard deviations adjusted to improve the computer skills of children who suffer from mental disability to the post respond according to the variable of the study (teaching style)

Teaching Style	Amended mean	Standard deviation
Normal	4.959	0.19
Educational program	8.841	0.19

Table (4): Results of analysis of variance on the analysis of the arithmetic means for improving computer skills in children suffering from mental disability to the post respond according to the variables of the study (teaching style and gender)

Source of variance	Sum of squares	Df	Mean of squares	Calculated F	Statistical significance	Practical significance
Computer skills	62.935	1	62.935	59.273	0.000	51.87%
Normal	217.141	1	217.141	204.506	0.000	78.81%
Gender	0.233	1	0.233	0.219	0.642	0.40%
Teaching style * gender	1.739	1	1.739	1.638	0.206	2.89%
Error	58.398	55	1.062			
Total	309.400	59				

As shown in table (2) there is a virtual difference between arithmetic averages for improving computer skills among children who suffer from mental disability for the post respond according to the variables of the study (teaching style and gender) and the Interactive variable between them (teaching style and gender), and to identify which children for the benefit of any of the two groups was a fundamental difference, The two amended

means to improve the computer skills of children with mental disabilities dimensional response were calculated, according to the variable of the study (teaching style), so as in the table (3).

It is shown in table (3), that the essential difference was in favor of the children of the experimental group by arithmetic mean of (8.841) than children from the control group who received the normal method of teaching with arithmetic mean of (4.959).

To answer the second hypothesis which states that: **There is no interaction between the (used training program and gender) in the performance of children who suffer from mental disabilities in computer skills as measured with the tool of the study?**

In order to verify the substantial virtual difference mentioned above in table (2); associated analysis of variance was performed on the analysis of the arithmetic means for improving computer skills in children who suffer from mental disability to the post respond after neutralizing the arithmetic averages for improving computer skills in children who suffer from mental disabilities in post response, according to the study variables (teaching method, gender), and interactive variable between them (teaching style x gender) and so, as in the table (4).

It is shown in table (4) there is a fundamental difference at ($\alpha= 0.05$) between the two special means at the level of significance to Improve computer skills in children who suffer from mental disabilities to the post respond due to the Teaching style variable, as shown in the table (4), the absence of a fundamental difference in the significance level ($\alpha= 0.05$) between the arithmetic averages for improving computer skills in children who suffer from mental disability to post respond due to the variables of the study: (gender, interactive variable) teaching style x gender))

As shown in table (4), that the practical significance (impact size) to the variable of the study (teaching method) which reached (78.81%); which means that the null hypothesis was not rejected by coincidence, but the presence of large correlation between the study variable (teaching method) and improving computer skills in children who suffer from mental disability.

Discussion of the findings and recommendations

Hypotheses of the Study For the first hypothesis, which states that: **There were no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha=0.05$) between mean scores of mentally disabled children in the experimental and control groups in computer skills.**

The results relating to the first hypothesis showed no statistically significant differences at the level of statistical significance ($\alpha=0.05$) on the school observation checklist attributed to the teaching style variable, in favor of the experimental group; that is, that there is an impact of the educational program for the development of computer skills, which was applied to the experimental group to improve computer skills, and this result is attributable to:

The specifications of the educational program for the development of computer skills, which is characterized by scientifically, The program included an interesting and simple activities attracted the attention of mentally disabled children, and commensurate with the mental age to them, as this result back to the educational benefits, which is to build and design an educational program, which was based on the basic skills of a computer , where the educational program based on direct education and analysis skills method according to the individual educational plan which is prepared for each child of mentally disabled children in the experimental group of the study sample, where this method resulted in the activation of the role of mentally disabled children, and made them the focus of learning-process based on computer skills.

For the second hypothesis, this states that: **There is no interaction between the used training program and gender in in the performance of children with mental disabilities in the computer skills, as measured by the study tools.**

The results indicated that there is no statistically significant differences at (0.05) between the results of the experimental group students attributed to gender, and accounted for the overall interaction (2.89%) only which is a weak effect, that there is no difference in the responses of mentally disabled children, whether they are male or female on the school observation checklist, and this indicates that the acquisition has been the evolution of the gender at the same level, and this explains the impact of the educational program, which studied by the mentally disabled children regardless of gender of the learner.

And the researcher attributed the reason for the lack of gender differences in computer skills to the educational program to the similarity of the learning environment and activities that are used in the educational program in terms of skills, activities and training methods are similar capacity and mental preparations for both genders,

and their treating of the same software, and add to that the program is consistent with the developmental characteristics of both equality, as there are no barriers to the application of the program for both genders.

The results for the second hypothesis showed the lack of statistically significant differences at the level of statistical significance ($\alpha=0.05$) on the school observation checklist attributed to the interaction between the training program and gender; where effect size reached (89%) which is a very weak effect, meaning that there was no effect of the education program which was applied on the experimental group for the development of computer skills after using covariance analysis (ANCOVA) to test the interaction between gender and the program at the school observation checklist, and this result indicated that the change caused in the performance did not show significant differences to the process of interaction.

Recommendations

In light of the foregoing analysis resulting from the current research, the researcher provided some recommendations, which may have a benefit for the mentally disabled children and those working with them, namely:

1. Conducting studies on the impact of individual educational plan enhanced computer on other categories of individuals with special needs.
2. Preparing workshops for those working in the field of education of mentally disabled children in education for the development of electronic computer skills to children.
3. Target other variables other than those listed in the search.

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